

Shannon's Entropy from Dynamic Considerations?

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In a number of previous notes (1),(2), we have argued that the $P(x,y,z) = 1/V$ volume probability for an ideal gas may be obtained through deterministic Newtonian scenarios for which the time measurement has been removed. In other words, one does not need the idea of states or maximization of entropy to find this probability. We have also argued that the Maxwell-Boltzmann $C_{exp}(-e_i/T)$ may be obtained through a consideration of collisions with energy conservation. These approaches only find the probability, not Shannon's entropy.

Here we try to find the form of Shannon's entropy through dynamic considerations. In particular, we use the notion of a function $dF (1/V)$ matching $-P dV$. Pressure may be obtained from dynamic considerations of an ideal gas and involves the factor $1/V$. Thus, $-PdV$ yields dV/V and F should be \ln . Now, $\ln(1/L) = \sum \text{over } dx/L \ln(1/L) = \ln(1/L)$ and so is equivalent to an average of $\ln(1/L)$, the probability. A similar result should hold for $p(e_i)$ such that "d" of this function yields dE . We show this is the case, i.e. that one uses: $-\sum \text{over } i p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i))$. Thus, it seems that one does not have to consider factorial expressions and various state arrangements, but may obtain Shannon's entropy directly from a dynamic expression, albeit one associated with an equilibrium gas.

Probabilities from Dynamic Considerations

In (1) and (2), we argued that $P(x,y,z)$ may be obtained directly from two different kinds of dynamical considerations. The first involves two 1-D boxes of lengths L and $2L$. Two particles start at $x=0, t=0$ and move with v . Time measurements are removed. Then, a point x in the L box may be associated with a set of times. These times, applied to the $2L$, box map to two x points (3 for $3L$ etc). Alternatively in (2), we argued that $dx=vdt$ implies that the same time is spent in each dx and so the $P(x)$ is $1/L$. In terms of $p(e_i)$, we have argued that $p(e_1)p(e_2) = p(e_3)p(e_4)$ and is equivalent to $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$.

The point that we make is that one may obtain the probabilities directly through dynamic considerations, but this does not yield Shannon's entropy form.

Shannon's Entropy from a Factorial Expression

Shannon's entropy is often obtained from a factorial expression:

$\ln(N! / \text{Product over } i n(e_i)!))$ together with Stirling's approximation: $\ln(n!) \text{ approx} = n \ln(n)$ ((1))

An alternative way to obtain Shannon's entropy is through:

Probability of N runs ($N \rightarrow \text{infinite}$) = $\text{Product over } i p(e_i) \text{ power } (Np(e_i))$ ((2))

Taking \ln yields: $\sum_i N p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i))$ ((3))

These approaches are probabilistic in nature and not based on the dynamics of a physical system. They are not wrong, but we would like to see Shannon's entropy emerge directly from dynamics.

-PdV for an Ideal Gas

The form $d\text{Work} = -P dV$ for an ideal gas means that a wall of the container is moved slightly. This form follows directly from the Newtonian:

$F dx$ ((4))

If one removes time measurements and has a gas in equilibrium, then one may use averages, but the picture is still very much Newtonian and dynamical. The force of a particle striking a wall is proportional to: p (change in momentum from p to 0) and the number of particles per time is $N/V \text{ area} \cdot v$. In three dimensions, one has a factor of $1/3$ due to the three dimensions so:

Pressure = $P = \frac{1}{3} \text{Average}\{ p v N/V \} = \frac{2}{3} N/V \text{Average}(e)$ ((5))

From ((5)), it follows that:

$P dV$ is proportional to dV/V ((6))

If one considers $p(x,y,z) = 1/V$ and asks what function F in a dS expression matches ((6)), one has:

$F = \ln$ because $d \ln(1/V) = -dV/V$ ((7))

Now $\ln(1/V)$ is equivalent to:

$\sum \text{over spatial little cells } d \text{ cell volume} / V \ln(1/V) = \ln(1/V)$ ((8))

$1/V \ln(1/V)$, however, is in the form of Shannon's entropy (up to a sign).

This suggests that one apply this idea to $p(e_i)$, i.e.

$\sum \text{over } i \ p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i))$ ((9))

Given that this should match $dE = \sum \text{over } i \ e_i dp(e_i)$ one has:

$T \sum \text{over } i \ \ln(p(e_i)) dp(e_i) + T \sum \text{over } i \ dp(e_i)$ ((10))

$\sum \text{over } i \ dp(e_i) = 0$ because $\sum \text{over } i \ p(e_i) = 1$ ((11)).

Thus, it seems that one may obtain Shannon's entropy directly from the form of pressure which is a dynamic quantity based on Newton's mechanics. The probabilities themselves may also be obtained through dynamical considerations.

Shannon's Entropy and Maximization

We now ask: Why should one maximize Shannon's entropy subject to constraints in order to obtain probabilities?

In the above discussion, we knew the probability $1/V$ from dynamical considerations and found $\ln(1/V)$ by comparing with a dynamical pressure calculation. This led to the creation of an average:

$$\sum_i d \text{ cell volume} / V \ln(1/V) \quad ((12))$$

Given that $d \ln(p) = dp/p$, one has:

$$D \sum_i p_i \ln(p_i) = \sum_i \ln(p_i) dp_i + \sum_i dp_i \quad ((12))$$

The second term on the RHS is 0 and so if $\ln(p_i) = \text{Lagrange multiplier} * \text{variable of a constraint}$, then one has the form of a maximization subject to a constraint. For the $1/V$ case, the variable is 1 from the $\sum_i p_i = 1$ constraint, while for $p(e_i)$, the variable is e_i from the constraint $\sum_i e_i p_i$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that one may obtain Shannon's entropy from a dynamical consideration of $-PdV$ and $\text{Function}(1/V)$, where the probability $1/V$ is obtained from dynamical considerations (1), (2). Thus, one does not need to use factorial expressions or N -run probability products, but may use Newtonian scenarios which demonstrate the physics of the problem, we argue. The factorial or strictly probabilistic approaches seem to be a little more abstract.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Volume Information Entropy and Classical Mechanics (preprint, zenodo, 2025)
2. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Volume Information Entropy and Classical Mechanics 2 (preprint, zenodo, 2025)